

**POLYTECHNIQUE
MONTRÉAL**

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DEVELOPMENT OF A NOVEL ABRADALBE COMPOSITE FOR THE 3D PRINTING OF MICRO-SCAFFOLDS

A presentation by: David Brzeski, P. Eng., M. A. Sc.

Laboratory of multiscale mechanics

2023-08-02

Research Center for
High Performance Polymer
and Composite Systems

ICAO environmental objectives for 2050:

- 1- Reduce CO₂ emissions by 75%
- 2- Reduce noise level by 65%

- Reduce clearance
- Limit aerodynamic losses
- Blade tip sealing
- Preferential coating wear
- Decrease fuel consumption

Abradable coating [2]

LEAP-1A turbofan [3]

- Inefficient coating application:
 - Time-consuming,
 - Poor geometric control.
- Benchmark* coating cannot be functionalized.

Abradable coating application device [5]

Epoxy (Part B)

Hardener (Part A)

Hollow glass microspheres [4]

DESIRED TECHNOLOGICAL OUTCOME

6-axis robot with half a fan case

Multinozzle printhead

Benchmark

O1: Develop a printable abradable material

O2: Perform a functional characterisation

⇒ Acoustic & Abradability

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Aerotech printing setup

Pressure, $P < 4.55$ MPa
Speed, $u = [0; 300]$ mm/s
Nozzle DIA (tapered), $D_o = 250$ μ m

Extrusion head

Benchmark

Micro-scaffold design

BENCHMARK MATERIAL COMPOSITION

Thermogravimetric analyses

~~↑ Glass microsphere (GM) content = {25, 30, 35} wt.%~~

↓ Glass microsphere (GM) content = {0, 5, 10, 15, 20} wt.%

Fumed silica (FS)*

PROCESSABILITY OF TESTED MATERIALS

Process map of filled epoxy

20GM:0FS

15GM:7FS

Benchmark

FILLER INTEGRITY

Unbroken
microspheres

5GM:10FS

10GM:8FS

15GM:7FS

Crushed
microspheres

Benchmark

μCT cross-sections 50 μm

15GM:7FS

SHAPE RETENTION STUDY

SEM images of 3D printed micro-scaffolds with top view (a-c) and side view (d-e), showing post-deposition shape retention and filament roughness.

$$\text{Printability index: } \psi = c_1[\psi^{top}] + c_2[\psi^{side} + \psi^f] = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{A_p}{A_e} \right] + \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{h_p}{h_e} + \frac{4\pi A_p^f}{L^2} \right]$$

DIW PROCESS MODELLING

Process-related rheology, rotational and capillary data sets with power law fit.

Oscillatory rheology time sweeps, complex viscosity, with 1st order isothermal cure model fit.

$$\eta(\dot{\gamma}) = K\dot{\gamma}^{n-1}$$

$$\eta^*(t) = a_1 e^{b_1 t} + a_2 e^{b_2 t}, \eta_0 := \eta^*(t=0)$$

$$\hat{\eta} = \eta(\dot{\gamma}) \cdot \frac{\eta^*(t)}{\eta_0} = K\dot{\gamma}^{n-1} \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_0} (a_1 e^{b_1 t} + a_2 e^{b_2 t})$$

Material processing simulations

Printing speed prediction and measured for star blends at maximum pressure and a set time after mixing, DIA .250 μ m (tapered).

Acoustic sample section printing ($\times 35$ video speed)

- Programmed extrusion pressure adjustments to account for material gelation derived from time-shear models = controlled process for coating functionalization.

ACOUSTIC ABSORPTION

Printed acoustic sample stack

Kundt's tube acoustic performance setup

Hard-backed acoustic absorption coefficients of the star blends compared to the simulated absorption using the JCAL model [7].

- 3D printable epoxy systems contain hollow glass microspheres and/or fumed silica.
- High fumed silica contents improve material elasticity and enable shape retention.
- A modified empirical model predicts the flow behaviour of developed materials.
- Printing speeds up to $175 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ pave the way for large area industrial production, while retaining high-resolution features.
- Efficient sound absorbing micro-scaffolds are printed using the developed composites.

0GM:12FS μ CT scan

0GM:12FS

5GM:10FS

10GM:8FS

Multinozzle printing of EC3524 B/A Black filled with OGM:12FS, 50 mm.s⁻¹, on a heterogenous curved HTRT substrate [13].

- Questions?

- Further reading:

- **Brzeski, David** (2021). *Development of Thermosetting Composite Materials for Producing Multifunctional Coatings by Direct Ink Writing* [Master's thesis, Polytechnique Montréal]. PolyPublie. <https://publications.polymtl.ca/9131/>
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- Chauvette, Jean-François & Hia, Iee & Dermanaki Farahani, Rouhollah & Plante, Raphaël & Piccirelli, Nicola & Therriault, Daniel. (2023). *Non-planar multinozzle additive manufacturing of thermoset composite microsccaffold networks*. Composites Part B: Engineering. 256. 110627. 10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.110627.
- Pierre, Juliette & Iervolino, Filippo & Dermanaki Farahani, Rouhollah & Piccirelli, Nicola & Lévesque, Martin & Therriault, Daniel. (2022). *Material extrusion additive manufacturing of multifunctional sandwich panels with load-bearing and acoustic capabilities for aerospace applications*. Additive Manufacturing. 61. 103344. 10.1016/j.addma.2022.103344.
- Baptista, Josué & Fotsing, E.R. & Mardjono, Jacky & Daniel, Therriault & Ross, Annie. (2022). *Design and fused filament fabrication of multilayered microchannels for subwavelength and broadband sound absorption*. Additive Manufacturing. Volume 55. 10.1016/j.addma.2022.102777.